

INCORPORATING NANOSTRUCTURES INTO NEXT GENERATION (SUSTAINABLE) FIBRES

Milo S.P. Shaffer^{1,2}

¹Department of Materials, Imperial College London, London, UK
South Kensington Campus, London, SW7 2AZ, United Kingdom

²Chemistry Department and Materials Department, Imperial College London
White City Campus, London, WC12 0BZ, United Kingdom
m.shaffer@imperial.ac.uk, <https://profiles.imperial.ac.uk/m.shaffer>

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Nanostructured materials offer the possibility to improve the performance and functionality of existing structural fibres. There are broadly two strategies (Figure 1): One involves the incorporation of the nanomaterial into existing state of the art fibres, in order to address critical weaknesses and/or introduce new functions. Examples of this first approach include the development of nanostructured interphases on existing carbon and glass fibres. Here, the nanomaterial improves load transfer between the fibre and the matrix and reduce stress concentration. Surface grafting of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) by direct CVD provides a hierarchical fibre with two differing reinforcement length scales. The advantages of this approach are well known, but typically limited by damage to the substrate fibres, and difficulties with scale-up. Informed by flow modelling and “dynamic snapshots”, we have developed a continuous spool-to-spool process that produces controlled, uniform grafting throughout the tow. The products show excellent single fibre and small composite performance in thermosets¹ and thermoplastics², and are relevant to multifunctional applications such as structural health monitoring³.

Figure 1: Schematic showing two alternative strategies for exploiting nanostructures in fibres : a) spinning new fibre systems based on 1D nanomaterial precursors (left, showing a single-wall carbon nanotube based fibre)⁴ or b) modifying of an existing state of the art structural fibre with a nanomaterial enhancement (right, showing a PAN-based carbon fibre grafted with carbon nanotubes to reinforce its interphase.²

The second approach, which is more challenging but potentially more transformative, relies on the development of entirely new fibre systems from the nanostructured or nanocomposite constituents; however, new processes to assemble and orient the constituent nanostructures. One dimensional nanomaterials are particularly well suitable to unidirectional alignment in fibre formats. A wide range

of building blocks are possible, including nanotubes, nanorods, and nanowires, based on carbons, inorganic compounds, synthetic proteins, and biologically derived constituents; a variety of these options are explored here (Figure 2). In particular, individual perfect nanocarbon structures have exceptional properties; the challenge is often how to exploit their potential in real macroscopic systems. Whilst dry spinning approaches may be attractive, wet spinning is more obviously scalable and applicable. However, the formation of individualized solutions of functionalised single wall nanotubes (SWNTs) and graphenes is challenging. We exploit reductive charging to form pure nanotubides (nanotube anions) which can be redissolved, purified, or optionally functionalised, whilst avoiding the damage typically associated with sonication and oxidation-based processing.⁵ Nanotubide solutions form nematic phases which can be spun directly into coagulant baths in order to prepare functionalised SWCNT fibres in situ. Grafting of suitable polymer constituents can increase dispersibility of both nanotubes and graphenes and hence help to produce nanocomposite fibres with higher strength and strain to failure,⁴ as well as multifunctional performance as supercapacitors. Non-carbon-based analogues of nanotubes offer different functions. For example, composite fibres containing inorganic (imogolite) nanotubes can generate healable structural fibres, with exceptionally high performance.⁶ Imogolite nanotube dispersions also form liquid crystalline mesophases and it is possible to spin pure imogolite fibres, analogously to the carbon nanotube examples.⁷ The imogolite system has the advantage of water compatibility and the opportunity for in situ process monitoring through optical birefringence and x-ray studies.⁸

Figure 2: Schematic showing possible one dimensional nanomaterial building blocks for fibres

More sustainable fibre systems can be pursued by spinning bioderived nanomaterials, or by using nanomaterials to allow the spinning of lignin-based materials, for conversion into carbon fibre. Lignin-derived carbon fibers (CFs) are an attractive target for low-cost sustainable composite applications. Our lignin-based fibers are wet-spun using a low-cost (<\$1/kg) ionic liquid, N,N – dimethylbutylammonium hydrogen sulfate ([DMBA][HSO₄]) as the dope solvent and water as the coagulation bath.⁹ If the lignin is extracted from the biomass using an ionosolv approach based on the same low cost ionic liquid, it can be used directly as the feedstock for the wet-spinning process. This latter approach removes several process steps, including the need to dry the lignin powder during its isolation. An initial life cycle analysis (LCA) indicates that this new ionosolv approach offers significant scope to reduce the cost and global warming potential of lignin fibre production.¹⁰ Very low loadings of CNTs can be used as the spinning aid for this ionosolv process, yielding fibers containing up to 96% lignin solid fraction. The presence of CNTs increases the estimated carbon fiber yield from ~40% to 54%, a critical factor for

technoeconomic outlook of lignin-based carbon fibers. In addition to enabling fiber spinning and increasing carbon yield, the CNTs may also act as graphitization templates and provide direct reinforcement of the lignin-derived carbon matrix, improving mechanical performance. Although the fibres do not yet match the strength or stiffness of state-of-the-art PAN-based carbon fibres, they may nevertheless be optimized to offer useful performance across a wide range of sectors from automotive to construction. In principle, CNTs can be bioderived, offering a fossil free route to low cost carbon fibers using only renewable carbon sources.

CONCLUSIONS

One dimensional nanomaterials are well suited to incorporation in fibre systems, both forming new types of pure fibre or in composite form. The aspect ratio and dimensionality are compatible with a high degree of alignment and efficient packing in the spun fibres, but also often generate lyotropic liquid crystal phases that play an important role in processing. Wet-coagulation spinning can exploit these phases and is readily scalable via established routes, from lab scale batches, through lab scale continuous monofilament, multifilament, and upwards towards pilot scale. Nanomaterials often offer excellent mechanical properties due to their high perfect and confined defect sizes but can also introduce a wide variety of functional benefits, including electrochemical energy storage and self-healing.

As specific examples, pure and composite carbon and imogolite nanotube fibres show promise as ductile and multifunctional reinforcements. Carbon nanotube fibres are conductive, loading-bearing, and with high electrochemical capacitance, relevant to structural supercapacitors Imogolite provides an analogous structure to CNTs that is easier to manipulate and study by POM & XRD, providing in situ insight into processing steps and other phenomenology that can be applied across the nanomaterial fibre domain.

Biomaterials provide routes to “green” carbon fibres and consumer textiles New types of lignin-derived carbon fibres, processed using water & IL only, are particularly promising for their potential low cost and reduced environmental impact. The introduction of carbon nanotubes, combined with new lignins, can improve graphitizability, yield, and performance.

While these new nanomaterials-based fibres offer great promise for the future, their commercial implementation will require time and investment. Meanwhile, nanomaterials can already be used to improve the performance existing state of the art structure fibres. For example, CNT-grafted fibres offer improved structural properties, improving interfacial strength and composite compression performance, whilst offering multifunctional opportunities for enhanced conductivity and self-sensing. A new process allows continuous uniform growth throughout a 12k fibre tow, allowing potential integration directly into existing carbon fibre production.¹¹

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